

Decomposition of Dilute Solutions of Potassium Permanganate in the Presence of Salts of Fatty Acids as Catalysts : Part-II

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The catalytic properties of some of the salts of fatty acids were known for a long time¹⁻⁷ and this prompted the present authors to undertake the kinetic study of decomposition of potassium permanganate, at temperatures 30°, 40°, 50° and 60° by conventional procedure. Exhaustive readings were taken for a set of dilute KMnO_4 solutions in the presence of salts of fatty acids, and another set using potassium nitrate as an added electrolyte. The depletion of KMnO_4 was recorded by titration with oxalic acid and from these the authors have calculated the order of reaction employing first and second order expressions. Energy of activation is obtained for the potassium nitrate, from the plot of $\ln K$ vs $1/T$.

TRANSITION metal coordination compounds were found to be effective and versatile in chemical kinetics⁸, due to their electronic and structural properties, notably in d^7 and d^8 low spin complexes comparable to free radicals, carbanes and carbanions. The promotion of chemical reactions by coordination compounds or a catalytic decomposition of reactants by metallic salts and complexes is expected to be effected through various intermediate reactions.

In the present paper, we report catalytic decomposition of KMnO_4 in presence of transition metal salts of fatty acids. It will be seen, from results, that the salts themselves do not undergo any decomposition, whereas KMnO_4 is induced to get split so as to evolve oxygen, the order of reaction in all the systems not conforming to first or second order strictly. It will be our endeavour to show in our next communication that Freeman and Carroll's treatment⁹ of these very results which forms a subject of a new paper, taken at $dT/dt = \text{constant}$, yields the order ~ 1.7 . However the mechanism discussed therein has been given in brief here.

Experimental

Chemicals and Materials : The metal salts used in the preparation of salts of fatty acids in the present study were, chlorides and sulphates of AnalaR quality. The salts were prepared by double decomposition method and were recrystallised several times from benzene. The novel method to get extreme pure salt of fatty acids was to convert them into pyridine adducts, which came out as beautifully coloured crystals and then by careful and controlled pyrolysis of these adducts to recover the original salt by recrystallising in hot benzene in extremely pure form. The metal contents were analysed spectrophotometrically and polarographically wherever possible, measurements being taken on SF-500 spectrophotometer and Cambridge Pen Writing Polarograph No. 91333-1.

Results and Discussion

In the study of decomposition of dilute solutions of KMnO_4 by the salts of fatty acids of transition metals (Cr^{+2} , Mn^{+2} , Fe^{+3} , Co^{+2} , Ni^{+2} and Cu^{+2}), the known technique of deriving the values of rate constant (K), at temperature intervals of 10° by titration method and evaluation of the energy of activation from the plots of $\ln K$ vs $1/T$ was followed. From the titre reading of the spent KMnO_4 with time and by using the expressions for unimolecular and bimolecular reactions, the order of reactions could be established.

In the present experiment, 0.05 N KMnO_4 solution was taken in excess (about 150 ml), so as to avoid appreciable changes in its concentration when 5cc. of it were pipetted out for titration at the intervals of 60, 120, 180, 240 minutes and at 72 hours and to this, in the second set, was added 0.250 gms salts of fatty acids and the entire solution was thermostated at temperatures at which readings were subsequently recorded, that is, at 30°, 40°, 50° and 60°. At these intervals 5cc of KMnO_4 solution was pipetted out and titrated by standard procedure against (a) standard oxalic acid and (b) standard ferrous ammonium sulphate of equivalent strengths. The results with standard oxalic alone are reported here, the other titration being carried as a duplicate check which was accurate within 0.01 cc. burette readings and since the initial concentration was checked and rechecked the estimate of inaccuracy in the first order rate constant is about 0.2% and second order 0.5%. Micro pipettes and burettes, used in the experiment, were calibrated accurately. Before titrating KMnO_4 solution, it had to be centrifuged at 3000 RPM to precipitate traces of MnO_2 formed in the course of reaction. Each time, at various intervals of time and at various stages of temperature, the precipitated solid residue obtained after centrifugation was returned to the bulk of the KMnO_4 solution. The above experiments were repeated in almost all salts of fatty acids for the

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS AND ACTIVATION ENERGIES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES FOR SALTS OF FATTY ACIDS

Temp. °C	First order $K \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$	Second order $K \times 10^3 \text{ lit. mol}^{-1}, \text{ min}^{-1}$	First order $K \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$	Second order $K \times 10^3 \text{ lit. mol}^{-1}, \text{ min}^{-1}$	Energy of activation Ea Kcals.
Chromium-palmitate			Chromium-palmitate + KNO_3		
30	9.200	10.034	2.990	3.488	4.76
40	2.900	3.146	—	—	(-) +
50	2.900	22.389	3.206	2.150	2.89
60	3.900	3.037	—	—	(-) +
Manganese-palmitate			Manganese-palmitate + KNO_3		
30	7.100	8.240	9.200	13.090	- +
40	8.500	2.674	—	—	(-) +
50	2.500	7.378	4.800	4.328	- +
60	5.500	4.074	7.500	7.765	(-) +
Iron-palmitate			Iron-palmitate + KNO_3		
30	1.300	1.783	3.900	9.243	4.560
40	1.300	3.402	2.900	3.017	(-) +
50	2.900	2.404	2.650	2.699	6.76
60	2.070	4.850	2.900	3.0017	(-) +
Cobalt-palmitate			Cobalt-palmitate + KNO_3		
30	6.218	4.135	4.600	1.445	5.49
43	3.455	2.412	—	—	(5.51)**
50	1.842	1.314	0.400	0.681	2.00
60	2.994	2.539	4.804	2.177	(4.56)**
Chromium-stearate			Chromium-stearate + KNO_3		
30	1.800	1.822	3.900	0.666	9.15
40	2.000	1.985	3.200	2.966	(4.06)*
50	2.700	2.029	4.100	3.699	6.71
60	1.800	1.631	4.600	3.775	(4.00)**
Manganese-stearate			Manganese-stearate + KNO_3		
30	1.600	1.548	2.500	2.002	1.12
40	1.300	1.985	6.900	9.390	(1.92)*
50	2.700	6.167	3.400	2.712	2.01
60	4.300	4.370	4.100	4.018	(4.86)
Iron-stearate			Iron-stearate + KNO_3		
30	1.842	1.723	2.073	2.013	3.66
40	3.915	3.970	3.915	3.918	(7.29)*
50	2.073	1.257	2.303	2.303	5.79
60	2.994	2.767	6.218	3.815	(6.09)**

(TABLE 1 CONTD.)

Temp. °C	First order $K \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$	Second order $K \times 10^3 \text{ lit. mol}^{-1}, \text{ min}^{-1}$	First order $K \times 10^4 \text{ min}^{-1}$	Second order $K \times 10^3 \text{ lit. mol}^{-1}$	Energy of activation Ea Kcals.
	Cobalt-stearate		Cobalt-stearate + KNO ₃		
30	1.152	1.253	2.303	1.974	0.91
40	3.951	3.657	3.685	3.552	(3.88)*
50	2.533	2.165	3.685	3.082	6.07
60	4.300	3.121	3.684	3.605	(2.89)**
	Nickel-stearate		Nickel-stearate + KNO ₃		
30	4.130	2.870	3.590	2.980	0.74
40	4.290	3.700	3.730	3.350	(0.84)**
50	4.810	4.250	4.630	4.010	3.66
60	4.530	3.700	3.170	2.910	(3.89)**
	Copper-stearate		Copper-stearate + KNO ₃		
30	1.300	1.184	0.691	0.706	0.91
40	4.800	6.532	2.500	2.230	(0.67)*
50	2.700	2.652	1.612	1.271	1.10
60	2.764	1.109	4.600	1.806	(1.16)**
	Chromium-oleate		Chromium-oleate + KNO ₃		
30	2.300	1.851	5.200	1.240	3.25
40	3.200	1.326	3.600	3.126	(6.46)*
50	3.200	1.290	5.200	5.095	10.03
60	3.400	3.701	7.100	2.638	(14.59)**
	Manganese-oleate		Manganese-oleate + KNO ₃		
30	2.700	1.984	1.600	4.078	1.77
40	4.600	4.668	4.600	4.824	(3.37)*
50	1.600	2.964	5.200	3.285	1.21
60	1.100	1.142	6.100	0.973	(3.59)**
	Cobalt-oleate		Cobalt-oleate + KNO ₃		
30	0.960	9.921	0.382	13.227	7.62
40	1.600	20.157	0.423	26.455	(4.76)*
50	0.132	13.898	0.350	71.270	3.05
60	0.280	42.142	0.140	17.427	(6.48)**
	Copper-oleate		Copper-oleate + KNO ₃		
30	2.303	2.069	1.842	2.314	1.83
40	4.145	2.736	3.224	3.267	(3.15)*
50	3.685	2.905	2.994	2.486	2.20
60	2.764	2.217	2.303	1.494	(7.25)**

Values in the parentheses with one and two asterisks are in presence of KNO₃, calculated by first and second order kinetics respectively.
(-) + and - + : The Ea values could not be estimated since the points obtained were scattered to a great extent.

same temperatures and time intervals with an extra addition of accurately weighed electrolyte potassium nitrate. The values of rate constant (K) obtained by using first and second order expression, and the activation energies (Ea) are shown in Table 1. It also gives the rate constant and activation energies obtained in presence of KNO₃.

It was also ascertained, by titration, that the 0.5N KMnO₄ left alone suffered no deterioration even after 72 hours. The KMnO₄ solution, which had depleted due to loss of oxygen, was filtered and the residue which contained the salts of fatty acids were recovered by centrifugation and then treated with boiling benzene which dissolved the salts of fatty acids, these entire operations were carried out in quickest possible manner and the recovered salts were added to the bulk of KMnO₄ solution. It was found, in all the cases, that the original quantity of the salt of fatty acid was least affected in the decomposition of KMnO₄, thus proving beyond doubt that fatty acid salt itself does not take even an imperceptible part in the decomposition of KMnO₄. Exhaustive readings were taken for dilute KMnO₄ decomposition in the presence of salts of fatty acids and, in addition, in the presence of potassium nitrate as an added electrolyte. In the majority of cases, the readings did not fit in either the first order or second order kinetics.

It will be the attempt of the present authors to show that the order of reaction of this mechanism is 1.7 and hence to fit in the first order or second order expression is futile. However, through the scattered points which almost seem to fall on straight lines, lines have been drawn and checked by the least square method to calculate the energies of activation and are set out in Table 1. Since the salt itself remained perfectly intact and KMnO₄ suffered decomposition, energy must have been derived from the changes in the oxidation states of cation going from M⁺ⁿ → M⁺⁽ⁿ⁻¹⁾ state¹⁰.

Effect of an electrolyte, such as KNO₃, added to the systems studied, revealed that added potassium nitrate raises the energy of decomposition of potassium permanganate. It may be that ordinarily all salts used here are colloidal in nature and hence very effective as catalytic decomposers. But when KNO₃ is added in small quantities, probably the colloidal nature of the salt is partially destroyed and hence the effectiveness of the catalyst decreases to the same extent. The obvious result is the enhancement of energy required for the decomposition. For example in the case of Co-palmitate and Co-palmitate + KNO₃ system the energy of activation with KNO₃ is raised to 5.51 from 5.49 in the case of first order and 4.56 from 2.00 in the second order system when KNO₃ is added. The same observation is made in the case of Mn-stearate, Ma-stearate + KNO₃ where the Ea values are 1.12, 1.92 ; 2.01, 4.86 Kcals respectively. This trend is unmistakably found in the systems of Fe-stearate, Co-stearate, Ni-stearate, Cr-oleate, Mn-oleate and Cu-oleate. However, in Co-oleate, Ni-stearate and Cr-stearate it is surprising to find that the electrolyte has no obvious effect on the colloidal properties of the salt. Hence the contention of the

author that the added KNO₃ has the effect of weakening the catalytic property of the salts studied is generally obeyed.

The decomposition of KMnO₄ in acidic, alkaline and neutral media is a subject of much research. The intermediate species suggested in the decomposition of KMnO₄ are so diverse of the type MnO₄²⁻, MnO₄³⁻, MnO₃²⁻, MnO₃⁻, Mn(OH)₄, MnO₄³⁺, MnO⁺, MnO²⁺ that it is inevitable, that in explaining complex reactions some prediction regarding the species have to be made. Tompkins¹¹ suggests the main decomposition product as MnO₂ whereas Wiberg and Stewart¹² give two electron transfer mechanism in which reaction between pentavalent manganese and heptavalent manganese oxyanion takes place. Since it was found by the present workers that neither first order nor second order reaction rate satisfy fully the experimental observation, the probable mechanism which may come very nearly to show that the order of reaction is nearly 1.7 by Freeman and Carroll method⁹ and hence non integer, may be given as follows :

with intermediate rapid reaction

where *HCOO⁻ is the hydrophobic part of the salts of fatty acid and OH⁻ are the ions obtained from H₂O since the reactions were carried in neutral medium. The authors wish to give an alternative suggestion for mechanism of the decomposition of KMnO₄ as :

Since Freeman and Carroll's method has to be followed under different conditions where dT/dt is maintained absolutely constant and methods of calculations are quite elaborate¹³, it is the subject of a separate communication¹⁰.

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